

ISic3696

I.Sicily inscription 3696

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

found near the agora in 1966

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara
Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330084

1. Ἀγ,α,θάρχο τῶ Πολ ι [— —]
2. [— —]α.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 330084

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1093

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e Selinunte?. *Kokalos*. 21: 121-153. At 149 no.14 tav.33.1

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